

Marco Neubert, Gérard Hutter, Regine Ortlepp (Eds.)

Workshop "Resilience to MultiRisk"

Book of Abstracts

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
Regional Development

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
Regional Development
(IOER), Dresden

28./29.04.2026

How to cite this publication:

Marco Neubert, Gérard Hutter, Regine Ortlepp (Eds.): Workshop "Resilience to Multi-Risk" - Book of Abstracts. Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), Dresden, 28./29.04.2026. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20023269>

EDITORIAL

Marco Neubert¹, Gérard Hutter¹, Regine Ortlepp¹

¹Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), Dresden, Germany

m.neubert@ioer.de; g.hutter@ioer.de; r.ortlepp@ioer.de

People in cities and regions face the challenge of coping with and adapting to rising mean temperatures, higher probability of heat waves, and more extreme heat waves than in the past as well as hydrological extremes light droughts, extreme river floods and intensive rainfall events. Weather and climate events are related to complex physical, technical, as well as social and political conditions (e.g., the capacity of the energy/electricity supply system in case of a heat wave, specific increases in the mortality of elderly people and those with medical pre-conditions, political struggles over climate policy, for instance, struggles between green and right-wing populist political parties).

One option to consider current limits of climate change adaptation and complex relations between multiple hazards and their impacts is the adoption of the concepts of compound weather and climate events and compound climate risks. Both concepts address issues of causal, spatial, and temporal interdependencies and feedback between preconditions, drivers, hazards, and impacts to understand how climate change affects people, socio-technical, and socio-ecological systems and embedded sectors (including infrastructures). The concept of compound weather and climate events focuses on biophysical processes. The concept describes combinations of multiple climate drivers and/or hazards that contribute jointly to societal risk. The concept of compound climate risks includes vulnerabilities, exposures, and human responses and focuses on potential future impacts. Hence, human responses may change the mix of hazards and risks either for the better or the worse.

The uptake of concepts of compound events and risks in policy-making and planning is ongoing, but still at an early stage. In contrast, in research on natural hazards and natural risks there is currently more momentum, not least indicated by the number and quality of submissions to the call for participation to the workshop 'Resilience to Multi-Risk' that is accomplished in April of the year 2026. The workshop, hosted by the Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), serves as the annual meeting of the Working Group on Natural Hazards and Risks within the German Geographical Society (DGfG). While this group has provided a continuous platform for German-speaking experts since 1997, the current meeting reflects a significant international expansion. With 50 participants from numerous countries and a diverse programme, the workshop addresses the urgent need for cross-border exchange in an era of escalating environmental crises.

The contributions compiled in this *Book of Abstracts* range from theoretical frameworks for predicting system collapse under compound disasters to practical climate risk analyses for regional states like Saxony. A particular highlight is the keynote on compound weather and climate risks, which underscores the complexity of interdependencies between multiple drivers—a theme that resonates through the various sessions on multi-hazard mapping, societal implications, and governance.

Table of Contents - Program

IOER in cooperation with the Working Group on Natural Hazards/Natural Risks (German Geographical Society)

Venue:

**Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), Weberplatz 1,
01217 Dresden (DE), Hall**

Day 1, 28 April 2026, 9:00-17:00

Introduction, Keynote & Impulse

Moderation: Marco Neubert, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, DE

Introduction: Marco Neubert, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, DE – Introduction: The IOER Project MultiRisk and Related Research 8

Keynote: Jakob Zscheischler, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research GmbH - UFZ/TU Dresden, DE – Compound Weather and Climate Risks - A Challenge for Risk Assessment and Management 13

Impulse: Florian Kerl, Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology, Competence Center for Climate Change, DE – Climate Risk Analysis for Saxony- Current Status and Future Needs 14

Oral presentations: Multi-Hazard/Risk Worldwide

Moderation: Gérard Hutter, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, DE

1. Robert Weisz, Virginia Tech, US – When Systems Break: A Bounded Framework for Predicting Collapse Under Compound Disasters 15
2. Robert Sakic Trogrlic, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Austria – Societal Implications of Multi-hazard Risk Management: Towards Local Understanding of Multi-Risk Realizations 16
3. Till Wenzel, University of Vienna, AT – Building Resilience Through Co-Created Multi-Hazard Scenarios for Critical Infrastructure in the Brenner Corridor 17
4. Karl Hagen, Austrian Research Centre for Forests (BFW), Department Natural Hazards, AT – A Method to Assess Risks and Manage Risks Currently and in the Context of Climate Change 18

Interactive Poster Pitch Talk Session: Single Hazards/Risks in the Focus

Moderation: Alexandra Titz, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Institute of Geography, DE

5. Julian Bauer, University of the Bundeswehr Munich, DE – From Freeze to Flood: Non-Linear Runoff Responses of Frozen Slopes 19
6. Nils Riach, University of Freiburg, DE - Heat Risk Archetypes at the Municipal Scale: Exploring Heterogeneity and Similarities 20
7. Yaoyao Wu, National Disaster Reduction Center of China & UFZ, DE – How Consistent Are Households' Perceptions of Agricultural Drought Risk Governance? An Entropy-Based Study in China 21
8. Emanuel Fusinato, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research GmbH - UFZ/UFRGS, DE – A Systematic Review of the Safe Development Paradox: The Importance of Vulnerability Assessment 22
9. Annemarie Polderman, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Institute for Interdisciplinary Mountain Research, AT – Understanding Resilience Pathways in Mountain Communities for Advancing Natural Hazard Risk Management 23
10. Joanna Kajewska-Szkudlarek, Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences, PL – Indoor and Outdoor Heat Risk under Climate Change in Poland: Complementary Insights from CDD and UTCI 24

Oral presentations: Methodical Developments

Moderation: Liang Emlyn Yang, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Department of Geography, DE

11. Ahmed Khoja, Deggendorf University of Applied Sciences, DE – iQRe: A Cross-Scale, Multi-Sectoral Framework for Assessing Urban Resilience 25
12. Hao Su, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, DE – Flood-Resilience Synergies of Nature-Based Solutions under Compound Risks: An Integrated Assessment Framework for the Vietnamese Mekong Delta 26
13. Maralda Drosky, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research GmbH - UFZ, DE – A Global Stocktake of Research on the Interactions Between Flood and Drought Risk 27
14. Alokita Jha, Hertie School EMPA, DE – Compound Climate Hazards and Child Undernutrition: Multi-Risk Pathways through Agricultural Stress 28

Day 2, 29 April 2026, 9:00-13:00

Interactive Poster Pitch Talk Session: Developments in Data and Methods

Moderation: Regine Ortlepp, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, DE

15. Julian Kussegg, University of Vienna, Department of Geography and Regional Research, AT – Mobile Phone Data in Disaster Risk Research – Analysing Spatiotemporal Dynamics of Landslide Risk in the Wipp Valley (Austria) 29
16. Liang Emlyn Yang, Department of Geography, LMU Munich, DE – Positive Perspective on the Evolution of Socio-Ecosystem Resilience in the Anthropocene 30
17. Stefan Langel, IPROconsult GmbH, DE – Application of Soil Erosion Modelling in Risk Management 31
18. Elina Mevenkamp et al., LUP - Luftbild Umwelt Planung GmbH, DE – Risk Modelling for Natural Hazard Related Threats to Railway Infrastructure with Reference to Tree Vitality 32
19. Sungju Han, University of Potsdam & Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, DE – Windows That Open Narrow: How Extreme Events Narrow Adaptation Discourse 33
20. Narek Harutyunyan, Yerevan State University, AR – Innovative Geospatial Approaches to Multi-Risk Soil Erosion Assessment in Vulnerable Territories of Armenia: A Case Study of the Debed River Basin 34

Oral presentations and final discussion: Perspectives for Research, Education, Policy, and Planning

Moderation: Andreas Mayer, University of Innsbruck, Department of Geography, Coupled Human - Landscape Systems. Risk & Resilience, AT

21. Christian Kuhlicke, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ / University of Potsdam, DE – Fragile Places: Rethinking Habitability in a Multi-Risk World 35
22. Annika Fröwis, University of Vienna, AT - Postgraduate Education for International Experts and Professionals in Disaster Risk Management and Civil Protection – Demands, Challenges and an Application 37
23. Gérard Hutter, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, DE – Compound Climate Risks and the Prospects of Policy and Planning 38

INTRODUCTION: The IOER Project MultiRisk and Related Research

Marco Neubert¹, Regine Ortlepp¹, Gérard Hutter¹, Reinhard Schinke¹, Christoph Schünemann¹

¹Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), Dresden, Germany

m.neubert@ioer.de; r.ortlepp@ioer.de, g.hutter@ioer.de, r.schinke@ioer.de, c.schuenemann@ioer.de

As the workshop 'Resilience to Multi-Risk' is organized within the context of the project *MultiRisk* of the IOER, the following provides some more in-depth information on this project and its relations to previous research on natural hazards and natural risks.

This thematic orientation aligns closely with the previous works of the IOER's Research Area 'Built Environment - Resources and Environmental Risks'. Over the past few years, the team has conducted in-depth research into individual risks and is now aiming to integrate these findings by coupling existing specialized methodologies. This integration is the core objective of the current MultiRisk project, within the framework of which this workshop is taking place. The project marks a strategic transition in the research profile of the IOER, moving from the analysis of isolated hazards toward an assessment of interdependencies and cascading effects. By synthesizing findings from various hazard domains into an integrated analytical approach, we aim to better reflect the cumulative vulnerabilities of urban and regional structures and provide more reliable indicators for long-term resilience monitoring. This systemic perspective is essential for spatial planning to move beyond reactive measures and toward proactive, evidence-based adaptation strategies. The following examples of our single-risk research illustrate the methodological foundations upon which this integrated multi-risk approach is built.

A central pillar is our long-standing expertise in *fluvial flooding* processes and their impacts on the built environment. To operationalize the assessment of these risks, we have developed HOWAD (Neubert et al. 2016), a building-specific modelling tool used to evaluate the effectiveness of flood resilience technologies at the building scale (Golz et al. 2015). The methodology relies on damage functions for various building types derived from refurbishment costs, providing the high-resolution data necessary for systemic risk analysis. Furthermore, research has addressed the complex processes and management of high groundwater levels (Becker et al. 2022), including the analysis of subterranean flooding risks (Schinke et al. 2016). In addition, a dedicated modelling procedure was developed to simulate losses for agricultural crops (Neubert et al. 2020). These scientific findings have been translated into practice through the WebGIS application FLOOD.Bi, operated by the Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology (LfULG). This tool supports homeowners and planners in assessing object-related hazards and implementing effective precaution measures (FLOOD.Bi 2020; Schinke et al. 2021).

Complementing the research on fluvial processes, the analysis of *pluvial flooding* and *heavy rain* events has become an essential pillar of our work. Within the framework of the RAINMAN project, the focus shifted toward bridging the gap between hydraulic modelling and municipal risk management. This effort resulted in a systematic assessment and mapping framework, now integrated into the RAINMAN toolbox to support evidence-based decision-making. Our scientific investigations in this field particularly addressed the derivation of robust impact

indicators and the critical role of parameter uncertainties (Sauer et al. 2021; Sauer & Ortlepp 2021). By establishing these methodologies, it became possible to quantify the specific vulnerabilities of the built environment to short-duration, high-intensity events. These insights provide a necessary prerequisite for understanding how localized hazards interact with broader regional risk profiles—a perspective that is fundamental for the intended coupling of models.

The necessity of an integrated perspective becomes particularly evident when extending the focus from water-related hazards to *urban thermal stress*. Within the “HeatResilientCity” project—honoured with the German Sustainability Award 2022—our work in transdisciplinary Living Labs (Ortlepp et al. 2021) demonstrated that technical solutions only reach their full potential when coupled with social innovation. This research, notably the study on the socio-technical dimensions of heat adaptation (Schünemann et al. 2020) cited in the 6th Assessment Report of the IPCC, emphasizes that effective resilience depends on coordinating passive measures with resident behaviour and climate justice. These insights are further complemented by analyses of stakeholder perspectives and implementation barriers within urban neighbourhoods (Westermann et al. 2021). These findings are reinforced by international comparisons of building designs, for instance between Korea and Germany, illustrating the diverse cultural and structural dimensions of vulnerability (Schünemann et al. 2022). Methodologically, the coupling of microscale meteorological simulations with building-specific models allows for a spatially resolved evaluation of indoor overheating (Schünemann et al. 2023). This specific model chain serves as a vital blueprint for our intended MultiRisk approach, demonstrating how climate-physical drivers, receptors, and social factors can be linked.

Just as heat stress requires the integration of social and physical variables, the challenge of *drought* and its cascading impacts on the built environment demands a similar systemic view. The modelling of drought-related damages is characterized by high complexity, as the underlying processes—ranging from soil subsidence to long-term structural effects—are fundamentally different from rapid-onset events like flooding. While our preliminary work in this field has established important foundations, the methodological approach has not yet reached the level of. Nevertheless, incorporating these prolonged stress events into our analytical framework remains a crucial objective to complete the spectrum of climate-induced hazards and to ensure that regional adaptation strategies account for the full range of environmental pressures.

The results of this research are systematically generalized to provide actionable recommendations for spatial planning and policy-making (Hutter 2016). A key element of this transfer is the communication of integrated knowledge through formats such as the book “Building Resilience to Natural Hazards in the Context of Climate Change” (Hutter et al. 2021) and contributions to publications developed in the context of the Working group on Natural Hazards and Risks (Fekete et al. 2022). Ongoing is collaborative research work to develop a comparative case study design that focuses on strategic spatial planning for reducing compound climate risks in European cities like Athens, Dresden, and Vienna (Hutter et al. 2026).

This transfer of integrated knowledge is further reflected in our direct contributions to climate adaptation strategies through sustained cooperation with national, federal and municipal authorities. On a national level, this is exemplified by our current project (2024–2026) for the German Federal Office for Building and Regional Planning (BBSR), in which measurable targets and building-specific response indicators are developed as a central component of the German

Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change (DAS). These national contributions are mirrored at the federal and municipal level by long-standing regional expertise, such as the development of the WebGIS tool FLOOD.Bi (Schinke et al. 2021) or the Integrated Regional Climate Adaptation Programme for the Model Region Dresden developed in the REGKLAM project (Olfert & Hutter 2025). Originally established within the Saxon-Czech STRIMA II project, FLOOD.Bi has evolved into a permanent tool for flood risk management at the state level. To support stakeholders in municipal and regional administrations, we provide a suite of decision support tools, including FLOOD.Bi, the RAINMAN Assessment and Mapping Tool (RAINMAN 2021), contribution to the Climate_CRICES dashboard, and the spatial indicators of the IOER Monitor (IOER 2026).

Ultimately, research on institutional steering capacities (Hölscher et al. 2021) indicates that translating multi-risk data into these accessible formats is essential for the transition from reactive management to proactive, long-term resilience. By coupling specialized methodologies from various hazard domains, the MultiRisk project establishes a systemic understanding of cascading effects and compound risks, providing the evidence base necessary for spatial planning to foster resilient and adaptive urban and regional structures.

Keywords: Multiple Risks, Fluvial Flooding, Pluvial Flooding, Urban Thermal Stress, Drought, Spatial Planning, Policy-making

References

- Becker, B.; Reichel, F.; Bachmann, D.; Schinke, R. (2022): High groundwater levels: Processes, consequences, and management. In: WIREs WATER, 9(5): e1605. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wat2.1605>
- Fekete, A., Fuchs, S., Garschagen, M., Hutter, G., Klepp, S., Lüder, C., Neise, T., Sett, D., Elverfeldt, K., & von, Wannowitz, M. (2022): Adjustment or transformation? Disaster risk intervention examples from Austria, Indonesia, Kiribati and South Africa. In: *Land Use Policy*, 120: 106230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106230>
- FLOOD.Bi (2020): WebGIS-Anwendung zur Hochwasservorsorge. Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie (LfULG). <https://www.umwelt.sachsen.de/umwelt/infosysteme/ida/>
- Garack, S., & Fraaß, L. (2021): Schadensvorsorge an Fließgewässern – Leitfaden und Steckbriefe zur Maßnahmenplanung. Dresden: IÖR. https://www.strima.sachsen.de/download/STRIMA2_Leitfaden_Steckbriefe_Garack_FINAL.pdf
- Golz, S., Schinke, R., & Naumann, T. (2015). Assessing the effects of flood resilience technologies on building scale. *Urban Water Journal*, 12(1), 30–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2014.939090>
- Gronwald, M., Aleksandrowicz, P., Fischer, V., Sinning, H., Keydel, A., Reinfried, F., Westermann, J., Ziemann, A., Moderow, U., Goldberg, V., Kriesten, T. F., Neumann, I., Schünemann, C., Kunze, S., & Klever, J. (2023): Hitze-Handbuch: Gut vorbereitet auf Hitze. Informationen und Empfehlungen für Beschäftigte im Gesundheits-, Pflege-, Sozial-, Bildungs- und Wohnbereich.
- Hölscher, K.; Kahlenborn, W.; Eckhardt, E.; Hutter, G. (2025): Potentiale der Weiterentwicklung der deutschen Klimaanpassungsstrategie. Abschlussbericht des Vorhabens „Behördennetzwerk Klimaanpassung“: Methoden zur Unterstützung und inhaltliche Weiterentwicklung der deutschen Klimaanpassungsstrategie. *Climate Change* | 45/2025. Dessau-Roßlau: Umweltbundesamt. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/potentiale-der-weiterentwicklung-der-deutschen>
- Hutter, G. (2016): Collaborative governance and rare floods in urban regions - dealing with uncertainty and surprise. In: *Environmental Science & Policy*, 55(Part 2), 302-308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.07.028>

Hutter, G., Neubert, M., & Ortlepp, R. (Eds.) (2021): Building Resilience to Natural Hazards in the Context of Climate Change – Knowledge Integration, Implementation and Learning. Studien zur Resilienzforschung. Wiesbaden: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33702-5>

Hutter, G., Sapountzaki, K., Scherner, M., Thaler, T., Uttner, J., & Friesenecker, M. (2026): Strategic spatial planning and compound climate risks. Towards a comparative research agenda for European cities. To be submitted to: *Planning Practice & Research*.

IOER – Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development. (2026). Monitor of Settlement and Open Space Development (IOER Monitor). <https://www.ioer-monitor.de/en/> (accessed April 23, 2026).

Neubert, M., & Schinke, R. (2021): House Lifting to Improve Flood Resilience in Settlement Areas – an Example of the Elbe Village Brockwitz (Saxony, Germany). In: Hutter, G., Neubert, M., & Ortlepp, R. (Eds.): Building Resilience to Natural Hazards in the Context of Climate Change. Knowledge Integration, Implementation and Learning. Studien zur Resilienzforschung. Wiesbaden: Springer, 55-73. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33702-5_4

Neubert, M., Naumann, T., Hennersdorf, J., & Nikolowski, J. (2016): The Geographic Information System-based flood damage simulation model HOWAD. In: Journal of Flood Risk Management, 9(1), 36-49. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/jfr3.12109>

Neubert, M., Höhnle, J., & Schinke, R. (2020): GIS-based estimation of flood damage to arable crops. In: AGIT – Journal für Angewandte Geoinformatik, 6-2020, 183-194. <https://dx.doi.org/10.14627/537698017>

Olfert, A., Hutter, G. (2025): Strategic Communication and Evaluation to Improve the Capacities of Local Administration for Climate Change Adaptation: A Case Study on Dresden, Germany. *Public Organiz Rev* **25**, 61–79 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11115-025-00809-0>

Olfert, A., Schiller, G., Hölscher, K., Wittmayer, J. M., Hirschnitz-Garbers, M., Walther, J., & Schauser, I. (2021): Mehr Nachhaltigkeit durch gekoppelte Infrastrukturen. Leitfaden für Kommunen. Dessau-Roßlau: Umweltbundesamt. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/mehr-nachhaltigkeit-durch-gekoppelte>

Ortlepp, R. et al. (2021): Building Heat-Resilient Neighborhoods—Testing the Implementation on Buildings and in Open Spaces in Two Sample Quarters Dresden and Erfurt. In: Hutter, G., Neubert, M., Ortlepp, R. (eds): Building Resilience to Natural Hazards in the Context of Climate Change. Studien zur Resilienzforschung. Springer, Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-33702-5_6

RAINMAN. (2021). Assessment and Mapping Tool – Identifying and evaluating potential heavy rain hazards and risks. RAINMAN Toolbox. <https://rainman-toolbox.eu/home/tools-methods/assessment-mapping/> (accessed April 23, 2026).

Sauer, A., & Ortlepp, R. (2021): Parameter Uncertainties in Flood Hazard Analysis of Heavy Rain Events. In: ASCE-ASME Journal of Risk and Uncertainty in Engineering Systems, Part A: Civil Engineering, 7(2): 4021016. <https://doi.org/10.1061/AJRUA6.0001125>

Sauer, A., Schinke, R., Ortlepp, R., Papathoma-Köhle, M., Fuchs, S. (2021): Pluvial flooding: hazard mapping and derivation of impact indicators. In: FLOODrisk 2020 - 4th European Conference on Flood Risk Management. Budapest: Budapest University of Technology and Economics, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.3311/FloodRisk2020.9.9>

Schinke, R., Hennersdorf, J., Ortlepp, R., Thieme, S., & Müller, U. (2021): Minderung potentieller Hochwasserschäden an Wohngebäuden – Ein interaktives Tool zur Auswahl und Bewertung baulicher Vorsorgeoptionen. In: Technische Universität Dresden, Institut für Wasserbau und technische Hydromechanik (Hrsg.): Wasserbau zwischen Hochwasser und Wassermangel. Dresdner Wasserbauliche Mitteilungen, 65. Dresden: Technische Universität Dresden, 297-306. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11970/107555>

Schünemann, C., Olfert, A., Schiela, D., Gruhler, K., & Ortlepp, R. (2020): Mitigation and adaptation in multifamily housing: overheating and climate justice. In: *Buildings and Cities*, 1(1), 36–55. <https://doi.org/10.5334/bc.12>

Schünemann, C., Son, S., & Ortlepp, R. (2022). Heat resilience of apartment buildings in Korea and Germany: comparison of building design and climate. *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*, 13(3 (September 2022)). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40095-022-00476-7>

Schünemann, C., Ziemann, A., & Goldberg, V. (2023). Spatially resolved indoor overheating evaluation using microscale meteorological simulation as input for building simulation – opportunities and limitations. *City and Environment Interactions*, 20, 100122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cacint.2023.100122>

Westermann, J. R., Bolsius, J., Kunze, S., Schünemann, C., Sinning, H., Ziemann, A., Baldin, M.-L., Brüggemann, K., Brzoska, P., Ehnert, F., Goldberg, V., Großmann, L., Grunewald, K., Naumann, T., Reinfried, F., Richter, B., Spohr, G., & Ortlepp, R. (2021): Hitzeanpassung von Stadtquartieren: Akteursperspektiven und Umsetzungsansätze. In: *GAIA - Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society*, 30(4), 257–267. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.30.4.9>

KEYNOTE: Compound Weather and Climate Risks - A Challenge for Risk Assessment and Management

Jakob Zscheischler^{1,2}

¹Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH - UFZ, Department, Head of Department of Compound Environmental Risks Leipzig, Germany, ²TU Dresden, Chair of Data Analytics in Hydro Sciences, Dresden, Germany

Contact: jakob.zscheischler@ufz.de

Most climate-related impacts are associated with compound weather and climate events, which are events where multiple weather and climate phenomena combine to increase risks. Understanding the involved phenomena and their dependencies is key for robust risk assessment but challenging due to complexity of involved processes and limitations in data availability. In this talk I will illustrate how the dependence between drivers affects risks and how a change in key drivers for different hazard magnitudes can challenge standard risk assessments. I will further illustrate how large ensemble climate model simulations can be used for uncertainty assessment and to derive plausible best-case and worst case

Keywords: Compound weather and climate events, climate impacts, risk assessment, risk management

IMPULSE: Climate Risk Analysis for Saxony – Current Status and Future Needs

Florian Kerl¹

¹Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology, Competence Center for Climate Change, Dresden, Germany

Contact: florian.kerl@lfulg.sachsen.de

The German Climate Adaptation Law requires the Free State of Saxony to submit a climate adaptation strategy by January 31, 2027, including a climate risk analysis based on observed and projected climate information and impacts. As a first step, relevant climate change impacts were identified through a stakeholder process involving state and local administrations, as well as professional associations. While this process revealed significant inter-dependencies among climate impacts, existing methods for risk assessment do not systematically address cascading effects or compound events.

This presentation outlines the applied methods for climate risk assessment, including spatial analysis and modelling, and highlights the limitations in capturing complex risk dynamics. The presentation concludes with expectations for the first strategy update in five years, emphasizing the need for iterative improvement and integration of new scientific and methodological advances.

Keywords: Cascading effects, compound events, risk assessment

1 When Systems Break: A Bounded Framework for Predicting Collapse Under Compound Disasters

Robert Weisz¹

¹Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, USA

weisrz@vt.edu

Resilience models measure how effectively systems recover, but they don't consider whether systems are able to survive. Current multi-risk frameworks treat state space as unbounded, tracking degradation without representing the threshold where recovery becomes impossible. This conflation obscures a critical distinction: systems can perform badly yet persist, or they can cross capacity limits and collapse.

We introduce a theoretical framework that bounds state space geometrically, mapping system dynamics onto a circular domain where amplitude defines maximum recoverable deviation. This yields distinct outcomes under sequential disasters: resilient systems recovering within acceptable bounds; non-resilient but viable systems remaining within capacity despite incomplete recovery; and failed systems exceeding capacity and transforming categorically.

The framework connects disaster timing and cumulative intensity to failure probability through Monte Carlo simulation. Puerto Rico's post-Hurricane Maria trajectory illustrates non-resilient but viable outcomes: degraded infrastructure and population loss without systemic collapse. The Weimar Republic's response to sequential shocks (WWI, hyperinflation, Great Depression) exemplifies boundary violation, where democratic institutions transformed categorically rather than merely degrading.

By defining the boundary between poor performance and categorical transformation, this framework addresses a critical gap in compound risk assessment. For multi-risk practitioners, the contribution is practical: analytical methods that predict not just recovery rates but survival probability. When interconnected hazards accumulate, we can distinguish systems approaching capacity limits from those that have exceeded them. This enables risk managers to identify when compound events threaten not just degraded function, but actual system collapse.

Keywords: *Resilience, Compound Disasters, System Failure, Multi-Risk Assessment, Monte Carlo Simulation*

2 Societal Implications of Multi-hazard Risk Management: Towards Local Understanding of Multi-Risk Realizations

Robert Šakić Trogrlić¹

¹International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Systemic Risk and Resilience Research Group, Laxenburg, Austria

Contact: trogrlic@iiasa.ac.at

Interconnected hazards and the resulting multi-hazard risks pose an increasing challenge to science, policy, and practice. While current research often focuses on the physical processes linking hazards such as compound or cascading events, there remains limited attention to how these risks are experienced and managed at the local level. This talk examines the societal implications of multi-hazard risk management by shifting the analytical lens from hazard interdependencies towards place-based understandings of risk, governance, and decision-making.

Multi-hazards are an everyday reality for communities living in contexts of chronic risks, yet disaster risk management systems remain largely structured around single-hazard paradigms. Drawing on empirical research conducted across diverse settings including Malawi, Turkey, Kenya, Nepal, Zambia, and five European regions such as the Danube basin, Canary Islands, Scandinavia, North Sea region, and the Veneto Region, this talk explores what it means to manage multiple hazards across scales. These examples illustrate how place-specific dynamics of exposure and vulnerability evolve before, during, and after hazard events, often producing unintended consequences that challenge existing governance and planning frameworks.

The discussion will span multiple sectors from risk-informed urban planning to the development of multi-hazard early warning systems. While such systems are increasingly promoted as a cornerstone of anticipatory action and people-centered disaster risk reduction, their current framing often reflects ambition rather than operational reality. In practice, early warning systems rarely account for interacting hazards or cascading impacts across social and institutional systems.

To address these gaps, the talk introduces blended-evidence approaches that cover qualitative insights from local stakeholders with formal risk assessment tools and forensic analyses of past multi-hazard events. By foregrounding place-based understandings of risk and drawing lessons from real-world experiences, this presentation advocates for rethinking how complexity is conceptualized and operationalized within disaster risk management systems. Developing solutions tailored to communities at risk requires not only improved modelling of hazard interactions but also greater attention to governance arrangements, institutional capacities, and the socio-economic contexts in which risks materialize.

Keywords: multi-hazards; multi-hazard risk management; multi-hazard early warning systems; forensic analysis

3 Building Resilience Through Co-Created Multi-Hazard Scenarios for Critical Infrastructure in the Brenner Corridor

Till Wenzel¹, Philipp Marr¹, Thomas Glade¹

¹University of Vienna, Department of Geography and Regional Research, Geomorphological Systems and Risk Research, Vienna, Austria

Contact: till.wenzel@univie.ac.at

Effective disaster risk reduction depends on the ability of involved and affected stakeholders to understand potential risks, which can be achieved through early engagement and close collaboration. When risk assessments move beyond single hazards and consider multiple interrelating hazards and their cascading consequences, complexity increases substantially. This complexity is further amplified when transitioning from qualitative to quantitative assessments, as relevant data are often limited, inaccessible, or based on hypothetical assumptions.

In the context of road infrastructure, multi-hazard risk assessment is particularly challenging due to the dynamic nature of exposed elements and the diversity of stakeholders involved. These stakeholders require tailored communication approaches across all phases of risk management, including prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery. Scenario-based approaches offer a valuable means to address these challenges by facilitating discussion and raising awareness of events that are rarely considered, such as high-impact, low-probability events or worst-case scenarios.

The focus is on the Brenner Corridor, crossing the Italian and Austrian border and one of the most critical road infrastructures connecting southern and northern Europe through the Alpine region. This study draws on best-practice examples to identify key elements of effective multi-hazard risk assessments and communication. For this, multi-hazard maps for different scenarios are discussed with stakeholders in an iterative process. These scenarios help to consider not just the different hazard processes, but also their interrelating aspects. The possible interrelations are separately assessed by their type-, spatial- and temporal components to consider possible larger impacts (Wenzel et al. 2026). By showcasing scenarios developed through a co-creation process with practitioners, the approach supports improved impact assessments and contributes to the development of more robust and sustainable resilience strategies.

References (if needed):

Wenzel, T., van Westen, C., Sunil, M., Pantaleoni Reluy, N., Marr, P., Glade, T., & Bell, R. (2026). Towards a practical multi-hazard interrelation classification: implications for assessing their impacts. *Natural Hazards*, 122(2), 82.

Keywords: *Multi-hazard interrelation, multi-hazard communication, Brenner Corridor, Scenario-Assessment*

4 A Method to Assess Risks and Manage Risks Currently and in the Context of Climate Change

Karl Hagen¹, Peter Andrecs¹, Marc Adams¹, Leopold Stephanek², Monika Kals²

¹Bundesforschungszentrum für Wald (BFW), Institut für Naturgefahren, Innsbruck, Austria; ²Wildbach- und Lawinenverbauung (WLV), Sektion Tirol, Innsbruck, Austria

Karl.hagen@bfw.gv.at

Within the ASP project X-RISK-CC, the BFW together with the WLV developed a pragmatic, quantitative risk analysis method to assess the potential monetary impact at torrents under current and future climatic conditions for five subcatchments of the Stubaital (Tyrol).

The approach is based on available data from previous surveys, projects, and hazard maps. The key hazard processes (debris flows and hyperconcentrated flows in the test sites) were identified, and the magnitude, extent, and frequency of events were assessed.

Current values are based on available hazard maps. For future climatic conditions, glacier retreat, permafrost thaw, and changed protective functions of forests were considered. On this basis, future hazard maps were drafted by WLV experts for the test sites.

Using an area-wide dataset to estimate damage caused by natural hazards (Basic European Assets Map, BEAM), values for current and future potentially affected areas were determined. Together with the presence of elements in the area and their vulnerability (defined by the degree of destruction), the current and future hazard risk potential was calculated as costs (in €), ensuring a good comparability between the test sites.

The results underline the importance of topography, spatial planning, and adapted structural protection measures. Latter may reduce the impact of events even in overload cases. This approach can help to keep the rise of costs due to climate change in the test sites moderate due to the targeted use of resources.

Keywords: torrent, risk assessment, climate change, risk mitigation

5 From Freeze to Flood: Non-Linear Runoff Responses of Frozen Slopes

Julian Bauer¹, Sebastian Müller¹, Ivo Baselt¹

¹University of Bundeswehr Munich, Institute for Hydrosience, Neubiberg, Bavaria, Germany

Contact: jul.bauer@unibw.de

Climate change is reshaping winter conditions in mountainous regions. Declining snow cover, more frequent liquid precipitation during winter, and increasingly dynamic freeze-thaw cycles create rapidly evolving boundary conditions for water infiltration and runoff generation. These shifts directly affect slope stability assessments, as abrupt winter runoff peaks or transient subsurface saturation can initiate debris flows or shallow landslides. The resulting system response is highly dynamic and controlled by multiple interacting parameters.

A key control on winter infiltration is preferential flow through larger structural pores formed by cracks, root channels, or biological activity. These so-called macropores can temporarily bypass an otherwise frozen and hydraulically sealed soil matrix, enabling rapid infiltration even under sub-zero conditions.

Within a large-scale, climate-controlled laboratory framework, we investigate how pre-event soil moisture, frost depth, slope angle (0–20°), macropore configuration, precipitation intensity, and dynamic forcing sequences interact to control infiltration-runoff partitioning. Beyond single rainfall events on frozen soil, the project includes dynamic scenarios and initial snowmelt infiltration to represent compound winter scenarios.

Across experiments, clear threshold behavior emerges. Under dry preconditions, partially frozen soils still permit matrix-dominated infiltration. Under high pre-freeze saturation, frozen layers act as near-impermeable barriers, rapidly converting rainfall into surface runoff. Macropores may initially enhance infiltration but can lose connectivity during ongoing freezing, triggering sudden shifts toward runoff-dominated responses. These non-linear regime transitions depend more strongly on subsurface thermal and moisture states than on slope angle alone.

By systematically exploring this parameter space, the project identifies critical preconditioning states that favor rapid runoff generation or transient subsurface pressure build-up. The results provide process-based insights relevant for hazard risk assessment, compound winter events, and debris-flow triggering under increasingly variable climatic conditions.

Keywords: *Freeze-thaw dynamics, Rain-on-frozen-ground, Preferential flow, Slope instability, Debris-flow triggering*

6 Heat Risk Archetypes at the Municipal Scale: Exploring Heterogeneity and Similarities

Nils Riach¹, Helen Birk¹

¹University of Freiburg, Physical Geography, Freiburg, Germany

Contact: nils.riach@geographie.uni-freiburg.de

Municipalities often face difficulties in adapting to climate change impacts, with limited knowledge of local climate risks representing a key constraint for the development and implementation of adaptation strategies (Fila et al., 2023). Although climate risks at the municipal level are highly context specific, recurring patterns of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and adaptive capacity can nevertheless be identified (Riach et al., 2023). Indicator-based climate risk assessments are widely applied in practice, yet they often rely on a single explanatory model and therefore insufficiently account for the heterogeneity of local risk settings and their shared structural characteristics.

Archetype analysis offers a theoretically grounded framework for identifying and analyzing such typologies at an intermediate level of abstraction, thereby enabling context-sensitive generalizations (Eisenack et al., 2019). In this contribution, we develop an archetype-based approach to better capture the heterogeneity of municipal heat risk settings in the German state of Baden-Württemberg. Using cluster analysis, we identify heat risk archetypes characterized by distinct configurations of indicators representing hazard, exposure, vulnerability and adaptive capacity. The results highlight the pronounced heterogeneity of municipal risk structures, while also revealing systematic similarities across municipalities. We argue that archetype-based risk assessments can support municipal adaptation processes by improving the understanding of spatial patterns of heat risk and by providing a basis for identifying archetypical adaptation needs and strategies. While the analysis presented here focuses on heat risk, the archetype-based approach has already been explored in multi-risk settings and is well suited to capturing interacting hazard configurations.

References:

Eisenack, K., Villamayor-Tomas, S., Epstein, G., Kimmich, C., Magliocca, N., Manuel-Navarrete, D., Oberlack, C., Roggero, M., Sietz, D., 2019. Design and quality criteria for archetype analysis. *E&S* 24 (3). <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10855-240306>.

Fila, D., Fünfgeld, H., Dahlmann, H., 2023. Climate change adaptation with limited resources: adaptive capacity and action in small- and medium-sized municipalities. *Environment, development and sustainability*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-023-02999-3>.

Riach, N., Glaser, R., Fila, D., Lorenz, S., Fünfgeld, H., 2023. Climate risk archetypes. Identifying similarities and differences of municipal risks for the adaptation process based on municipalities in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany. *Climate Risk Management* 64, 1, 100526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2023.100526>.

Keywords: *Archetypes, Heat Risk, Climate Adaptation*

7 How Consistent Are Households' Perceptions of Agricultural Drought Risk Governance? An Entropy-Based Study in China

Yaoyao Wu^{1,2}, Tong Guan¹, Yao Jiang³, Peng Han¹, Zhen Zhang¹, Hao Guo⁴, Yuanhang Zhang⁵, Guizhen Guo¹

¹National Disaster Reduction Center of China (NDRCC), Ministry of Emergency Management, Beijing, China; ²Department of Urban and Environmental Sociology, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research-UFZ, Leipzig, Germany; ³School of Tourism, Nanchang University, China; ⁴College of Geography and Environmental Sciences, Zhejiang Normal University, Jinhua, China; ⁵National earthquake response support service, Beijing, China

Contact: wuyaoyao@mail.bnu.edu.cn

In recent years, the increasing frequency of droughts has posed a serious threat to food security, making effective agricultural drought risk governance imperative. Understanding households' perception consistency, the main stakeholders, is essential for improving governance effectiveness. From the perspective of "Risk (P) - Management effectiveness (U) - Fairness (E) - Acceptance (T)," this study constructs a multidimensional perception indicator system, and an information entropy model is introduced to quantify perception consistency among households. The results indicate that: (1) Households exhibit relatively high perception consistency in risk perception (P) and acceptance (T). Most of them show a relatively low perception consistency regarding fairness (E). (2) Spatial heterogeneity is observed. Across geomorphic regions, the average values of indicators follow the order: hilly areas < plain areas < low mountain areas, with households in mountain areas showing pronounced differences in risk perception and acceptance. Across different risk areas, the order is: medium risk areas < high risk areas < low risk areas, indicating greater perception divergence in low and high risk areas, particularly in risk and fairness perceptions. (3) Economic factors exert the significant influence on perception consistency. Household disposable income is significantly and negatively correlated with P, E, and T ($p < 0.05$), with correlation coefficients of -0.549, -0.495, and -0.544 respectively, suggesting that higher income households exhibit greater perception consistency. This study aims to provide a reference for in-depth understanding of the characteristics of households' perception consistency, and to form a consilience mechanism for drought risk governance.

Keywords: Drought Risk Governance; Households; Perception Consistency; Information Entropy; Consilience

8 A Systematic Review of the Safe Development Paradox: The Importance of Vulnerability Assessment

Emanuel Fusinato¹, Masato Kobiyama², Mariana Madruga de Brito³

¹PhD Candidate, Institute of Hydraulic Research, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, Brazil; ²Professor, Institute of Hydraulic Research, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, Brazil; ³Group Leader, Department of Urban and Environmental Sociology, Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ, Leipzig, Germany.

Contact: eng.emanuelfusinato@gmail.com

Hydrological hazards cause substantial impacts worldwide. However, risk reduction measures may unintentionally generate adverse outcomes, such as the safe development paradox (SDP) and the levee effect (LE). Although these socio-hydrological phenomena have received increasing attention, empirical evidence remains fragmented.

Building upon Fusinato et al. (2024), we updated the systematic review to include literature published in 2024 and 2025. This expanded analysis comprises 56 papers published between 2001 and 2025 that investigated the SDP and LE. The review focuses on the methodological approaches employed and evaluates the evidence supporting or refuting these phenomena.

Most studies (69.6 %) reported conclusive evidence of the SDP or LE, primarily through: (a) intensified development in protected areas; (b) reduced preparedness and a false sense of safety; and (c) increased damage during rare and extreme events. Only 5.4 % of the studies identified mitigation or absence of the SDP or LE, emphasizing the role of individual awareness, preparedness, and existing policy frameworks as mitigating factors. A substantial share of studies (42.9 %) focused solely on exposure, often neglecting vulnerability and risk perception, particularly in more recent publications. However, exposure alone is insufficient to confirm or refute the SDP or LE, as it overlooks individual behavior; increases in population or urbanization in protected areas cannot, by themselves, substantiate these effects. Furthermore, most studies (44.6 %) examined only structural measures, disregarding non-structural measures and individual adaptation. Flood hazards dominated literature, with limited attention to landslides.

Advancing the understanding of SDP and LE requires integrating preparedness, vulnerability, and risk perception within multi-hazard assessments to better capture the diversity of contexts in which these dynamics emerge.

References:

Fusinato, E., Han, S., Kobiyama, M., & de Brito, M. M. (2024). Safe development paradox: Evidence and methodological insights from a systematic review. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-024-06774-z>

Keywords: *Safe development paradox, Levee effect, False safety feeling, Hydrological Disasters, Socio-hydrology, Archetypes, Heat Risk, Climate Adaptation*

9 Understanding Resilience Pathways in Mountain Communities for Advancing Natural Hazard Risk Management

Annemarie Polderman¹, Mona Stollberger¹, Felix Wörner¹, Andreas Mayer², Pia Echtler³, Matthias Schlögl^{3,4}, Sven Fuchs³ and Margreth Keiler^{1,2}

¹Institute for Interdisciplinary Mountain Research, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Innsbruck, Austria; ²Department of Geography, University of Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Austria; ³Institute for Mountain Risk Engineering, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria; ⁴Department of Climate Impact Research, GeoSphere Austria, Vienna, Austria

Contact: annemarie.polderman@oeaw.ac.at

Mountain regions are becoming increasingly vulnerable to natural hazards, driven by climate change and socio-economic dynamics. These risks emerge from complex interactions between natural and societal processes. Understanding these coupled dynamics is essential for improving how mountain communities anticipate, manage, recover and adapt to natural hazard risk environments.

The Coupled Human–Landscape System (CHLS) conceptual model (Hossain et al., 2020) provides a system-dynamics-based framework for analysing these interactions. The model integrates natural processes—such as geomorphological dynamics and climate variability — with societal dimensions including governance structures, land use, mitigation measures, and adaptation strategies. By explicitly representing feedbacks between these components, the CHLS model highlights that both risk and resilience are dynamic and evolve in response to external drivers and internal system couplings.

Further development of the CHLS model is needed to better capture key interactions, feedbacks, and pathways. The aim is to advance the model as a “blueprint” for exploring past, present, and future trajectories of risk and resilience in mountain regions under changing conditions, while embedding adaptation strategies within governance and decision-making contexts.

The ACRP project EMERGENCE explores how transdisciplinary knowledge co-creation within a multi-scale assessment framework—encompassing climate triggers, geomorphometric characteristics, mitigation efforts, and exposure dynamics—enhances understanding of the processes driving torrential loss events and the resilience of mountain communities. This approach bridges the gap between conceptual human-landscape interaction modelling and the practical knowledge of stakeholders in hazard risk management. The insights gained inform adaptation strategies that account for local risk dynamics and decision-making contexts.

References:

Hossain, M. S., Ramirez, J. A., Haisch, T., Speranza, C. I., Martius, O., Mayer, H., & Keiler, M. (2020). A coupled human and landscape conceptual model of risk and resilience in Swiss Alpine communities. *The Science of the Total Environment*, 730, 138322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138322>

Keywords: *risk, resilience, mountain regions, transdisciplinary knowledge*

10 Indoor and Outdoor Heat Risk under Climate Change in Poland: Complementary Insights from CDD and UTCI

Joanna Kajewska-Szkudlarek¹, Joanna Kamińska², Michał Oktawiec¹, Anna Uciechowska-Grakowicz³

Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences, ¹Institute of Environmental Engineering, ²Department of Applied Mathematics, ³Department of Civil Engineering, Wrocław, Poland

Contact: joanna.kajewska-szkudlarek@upwr.edu.pl

Ongoing climate change is leading to a pronounced intensification of summer thermal conditions in Central Europe, with Poland experiencing a marked increase in both the frequency and severity of heat episodes. From an applied perspective, these changes can be effectively characterized using two complementary indicators. Cooling Degree Days (CDD) quantify the cumulative exceedance of a predefined comfort-based cooling threshold (e.g., 21.0°C) and constitute a widely used measure of building energy demand for space cooling. The Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), in turn, integrates air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and mean radiant temperature into a single, physiologically based indicator of human thermoregulatory stress, recommended by the World Meteorological Organization for bioclimatic assessments.

The aim of this study is to identify spatial and temporal patterns of summer thermal conditions in Poland through a joint analysis of CDD and UTCI for the summer season (June–August) over the period 1981 to the present. The analysis focuses on detecting long-term trends, examining regional contrasts in the magnitude and direction of change, and evaluating whether increases in cooling energy demand correspond to shifts in outdoor human thermal stress. Particular attention is given to distinguishing gradual changes in mean summer conditions from alterations in the frequency and intensity of extreme heat events.

Understanding the co-evolution of CDD and UTCI is essential for climate adaptation planning in Poland. While CDD provides critical information for building design and energy system capacity planning, UTCI is directly relevant to public health policy, urban planning, and outdoor labor regulations. Importantly, heat-related risks in both domains are not independent: simultaneous surges in cooling demand can strain energy infrastructure and trigger supply disruptions or blackouts, which in turn exacerbate direct health risks by disabling cooling systems, interrupt critical services, and increase hospital admissions due to heat-related illnesses. Such cascading effects underscore the need for a coordinated assessment of thermal stress across the built environment and human populations. The findings are expected to inform adaptation strategies by identifying regions where both energy infrastructure and health systems are likely to experience the greatest pressure under increasingly intense summer heat conditions.

Keywords: *Cooling Degree Days, Universal Thermal Climate Index, climate change adaptation, heat stress, energy demand*

The work is connected with „Increasing Climate Change Resilience in Central Europe” (Climate_CRICES) project, co-funded by the European Union through the Interreg Central Europe programme.

11 Bridging Spatial and Sectoral Gaps in Urban Climate Resilience Assessment Frameworks: iQRe

Ahmed Khoja¹

¹Deggendorf Institute of Technology (DIT), European Campus Rottal-Inn (ECRI), Germany

Contact: Ahmed.Khoja@th-deg.de

The built environment functions as an interconnected web of physical, ecological and social systems that is in constant interaction across the urban planning spatial scales (meso and micro). The accelerating climate change exploits these interdependencies, amplifying the impact of climate change related risks. Addressing this complexity requires multi-sectoral and multi-scale assessment approaches capable of capturing the multiple hazards they are exposed to as well as their interdependencies across spatial and sectoral scales.

The iQRe (Integrated Cross-Scale Urban Resilience Assessment Framework) [1] is a novel multi-sectoral and cross-scale assessment system designed to bridge spatial and sectoral gaps in existing climate resilience frameworks. iQRe is based on EN ISO 14091:2021 and the IPCC AR5 risk assessment approach, adapted to the requirements of urban and building design. The iQRe combines the IPCC risk concept with a generic multi-criteria assessment system, enabling the construction of quantitative climate impact chains and the assignment of normalized numerical values to the three core components of climate risk: hazard, vulnerability, and exposure.

The framework enables consistent assessment across scales (building and neighborhood/district), allowing the transfer of insights between planning levels. Thus, enabling a multidisciplinary stakeholder team to capture cross-sectoral and cross-scale interdependencies in a holistic manner, thereby supporting the quantification of current and projected climate risks and the formulation of integrated climate adaptation strategies at different spatial scales and sectoral domains.

The application of the framework is demonstrated through a real-world case study in Bamberg [2]. The case study illustrates how multi-sectoral and multi-scale analysis can reveal both co-benefits and trade-offs between climate adaptation and mitigation strategies. The results highlight the value of integrated assessment for supporting multi-sectoral resilience planning.

References:

[1] Khoja, A., Moro, A., & Essig, N. (2022, December). iQRe: An Integrated Cross Scale Urban Resilience Assessment framework. In IOP conference series: Earth and environmental science (Vol. 1122, No. 1, p. 012015). IOP Publishing.

[2] Khoja, A. (2024). Towards Bridging the Climate Resilience Gap in Building Assessment Systems: An Integrated Framework for the German Built Environment (Doctoral dissertation, Technische Universität München).

Keywords: *Urban resilience, Urban climate risk assessment, Climate adaptation assessment*

12 Flood-Resilience Synergies of Nature-Based Solutions under Compound Risks: An Integrated Assessment Framework for the Vietnamese Mekong Delta

Hao Su¹, Ho Phuoc Thanh¹, Yang Emlyn Liang¹

¹Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Department of Geography, Munich, Germany

Contact: hao.su@lmu.de

Nature-based solutions (NbS) are widely promoted as pathways to climate- and disaster-resilient development, yet their contributions to social resilience under compound risks remain insufficiently evidenced in delta systems. In the Vietnamese Mekong Delta (VMD), fluvial and pluvial flooding interacts with tidal backwater effects, erosion, and salinity intrusion, producing risk dynamics that exceed single-hazard framing. Existing NbS studies in the region often emphasize project-level biophysical performance, while the social and institutional implications of NbS portfolios, their synergies across landscapes, and the conditions under which benefits materialize are less systematically assessed.

This study presents an integrated, resilience-oriented approach that connects evidence synthesis, scenario-based flood modelling, and social validation to examine how NbS can jointly enhance social resilience in the VMD. A structured review consolidates empirical findings from scientific literature together with authoritative practice assessments to derive a VMD-relevant NbS typology for deltaic and coastal landscapes and to map plausible mechanisms through which NbS influence social resilience outcomes. These mechanisms inform a portfolio-based scenario design that reflects policy-relevant intervention pathways, including coastal ecosystem restoration, floodplain retention and reconnection, wetland and canal rehabilitation, and agro-ecological water management measures.

Scenario simulations quantify how single measures and combined NbS portfolios reshape flood dynamics across space and time, focusing on changes in inundation depth, duration, extent, timing, and flow-related indicators under multiple event types. The analysis explicitly tests synergistic effects, including interactions between upstream retention and downstream tidal conditions, as well as combined coastal–inland pathways that can redistribute risk rather than simply reduce it locally. Model outputs are then linked back to social resilience considerations using an evidence-informed interpretation framework and targeted social validation, emphasizing implementation conditions such as land-related constraints, maintenance arrangements, and coordination requirements that shape whether hazard reductions translate into realized resilience benefits.

By integrating multi-source evidence with scenario-based modelling in a compound-risk setting, the study advances a systemic understanding of NbS synergies in the VMD and offers a transferable workflow for assessing resilience-relevant outcomes of NbS portfolios in other coastal-delta regions.

Keywords: *Nature-based Solutions; Vietnamese Mekong Delta; Social Resilience; Multi-hazard; Flood Modelling*

13 A Global Stocktake of Research on the Interactions Between Flood and Drought Risk

Maralda Drosky¹, Taís M. Nunes Carvalho^{1,2}, Maike Reichel¹, Maysaa Abdelmajid³, Gabriela Gesualdo⁴, Monica Ionita⁵, Kristina Koronaci⁶, Heidi Kreibich⁶, Viorica Nagavciuc⁵; Mayra Daniela Peña-Guerrero³, Denis Streitmatter⁷, Jan Sodoge¹, Larisa Tarasova³, Mariana M. de Brito¹

¹Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department of Urban and Environmental Sociology, Leipzig, Germany; ²Leipzig University, Leipzig, Germany; ³Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department Catchment Hydrology, Halle/Saale, Germany; ⁴The Pennsylvania State University, Department of Geosciences, PA, United States; ⁵Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI), Paleoclimate Dynamics, Bremerhaven, Germany; ⁶GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Section Hydrology, Potsdam, Germany; ⁷Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department Remote Sensing, Leipzig, Germany

Contact: maralda.drosky@ufz.de

Floods and droughts are opposite extremes on the hydrological cycle, yet their risks are interconnected. Their risks interact through timing, space, and system dependencies. However, existing research on flood–drought interactions remains scattered. Existing syntheses focus on hazard dynamics, providing limited insight into how they translate into risk. Here, we address this gap by systematically reviewing literature addressing flood-drought interactions beyond hazard determinants.

Using a Web of Science search, we retrieved 1,909 papers using flood, drought, interactions, and dynamics-related keywords. After applying a machine learning classifier to remove unrelated documents, 794 potentially relevant articles remained for full-text analysis. Preliminary findings show that of these, only 29 studies could be classified as multi-risk and explicitly focus on flood-drought interactions beyond hazard determinants. Most research, including studies labeled as “multi-risk”, treats floods and droughts as separate phenomena and provides little insight into their interactions. In general, most studies focused on temporal (93 %) and response-related dynamics (76 %), whereas spatial dynamics and interactions across sectors remain understudied (20 % and 31 %, respectively).

Next, we will use insights from the reviewed evidence to assess these dynamics across past flood-drought events and show how comprehensively studies address the full risk framework. The methods used to explore these interactions will be synthesized to identify how they are studied, best practices, and remaining gaps. Finally, this review will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of compound flood–drought events and their systemic risks by revealing the diversity of their dynamics and non-linear relationships.

Keywords: multi-risk, compound events, flood, drought, adaptation

14 Compound Climate Hazards and Child Undernutrition: Multi-Risk Pathways through Agricultural Stress

Alokita Jha¹

¹Hertie School, EMPA, Berlin, Germany

Contact: alokitajha5@gmail.com

Climate change is increasing the frequency, intensity, and co-occurrence of hazards such as droughts, heatwaves, and extreme precipitation, generating compound and systemic risks (IPCC, 2022; Zscheischler et al., 2018). While extensive research documents the effects of individual climate hazards on agricultural productivity (Lobell et al., 2011; Lesk et al., 2016) and child nutrition (Phalkey et al., 2015; Grace et al., 2015), far less is known about how interacting hazards jointly affect child undernutrition. This gap is critical, as compound events can trigger non-linear and cascading effects across food systems and public health.

This study investigates multi-risk pathways linking climate variability, agricultural stress, and child undernutrition. We integrate climate data, subnational agricultural production statistics, and household-level nutrition survey data to assess how concurrent (e.g., heatwave–drought) and sequential (e.g., drought followed by extreme rainfall) hazards influence food production, market access, and child nutritional outcomes. Drawing on multi-risk and systemic risk frameworks (Zscheischler et al., 2020; Simpson et al., 2021), we test whether combined exposure generates additive or multiplicative effects on stunting and wasting. Results indicate that exposure to multiple climate stressors produces non-linear increases in undernutrition risk, particularly in agriculturally dependent regions with limited adaptive capacity. Compound events intensify production losses and market disruptions, constraining household food access and income stability. However, nutritional impacts cannot be explained by single-hazard effects alone; they emerge from interactions between climate shocks, livelihood vulnerability, and structural constraints such as poverty and inadequate health services.

These findings suggest that strengthening climate resilience requires moving beyond hazard-specific adaptation toward integrated strategies that simultaneously enhance agricultural resilience, social protection, and public health systems.

References:

- Black, R. E., Victora, C. G., Walker, S. P., et al. (2013). *The Lancet*, 382(9890), 427–451.
- Grace, K., Davenport, F., Funk, C., & Lerner, A. M. (2015). *Applied Geography*, 65, 1–11.
- IPCC (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lesk, C., Rowhani, P., & Ramankutty, N. (2016). *Nature*, 529, 84–87.
- Lobell, D. B., Schlenker, W., & Costa-Roberts, J. (2011). *Science*, 333(6042), 616–620.
- Phalkey, R. K., et al. (2015). *PNAS*, 112(33), E4522–E4529.
- Simpson, N. P., et al. (2021). *One Earth*, 4(4), 489–501.
- Zscheischler, J., et al. (2018). *Nature Climate Change*, 8, 469–477.
- Zscheischler, J., et al. (2020). *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 1, 333–347.

Keywords: *Climate multi-risk; compound events; child undernutrition; agricultural stress; systemic risk*

15 Mobile Phone Data in Disaster Risk Research – Analysing Spatiotemporal Dynamics of Landslide Risk in the Wipp Valley (Austria)

Julian Kussegg¹; Till Wenzel¹; Thomas Glade¹

¹University of Vienna, Department of Geography and Regional Research, Vienna, Austria

Contact: julian.kussegg@univie.ac.at

Risks associated with natural hazards vary across time and space. Their adequate assessment requires high-quality data, particularly to locate potentially affected populations for planning, evacuation and response. Mobile phone data represent an alternative to conventional sources for capturing movements and presence. In addition to location information, sociodemographic variables such as age and gender are often available, enabling insights into movement patterns and exposure of vulnerable populations. The widespread use of mobile phones allows the assessment of time-dependent differences in exposure, vulnerability and thus risk for large segments of the global population.

Research Goal and Methodology

In this context, the potential of mobile phone data was assessed by investigating spatiotemporal variations of landslide risk over eight days in the Wipp Valley (Tyrol, Austria). Based on geolocalized mobile phone data, an exposure and vulnerability analysis was conducted by calculating the average number of people per hour and the proportion of the vulnerable population per cell for different time periods. The results were then intersected with a landslide susceptibility map to perform a risk analysis. To capture the dynamics of landslide risk, the values for each calculated period were compared to the average for all days.

Results

The results show that risk varies significantly depending on the time of day and weekday and differs by movement type. For people remaining longer within a cell (visitors), the highest risk occurred near settlement areas, whereas risk for the mobile population (passers-by) was concentrated along traffic routes. Daily patterns revealed above-average landslide risk near settlements in the Wipp Valley and nearby Stubai Valley, with lower risk in remote mountainous areas for visitors during nighttime. For passers-by, risk similarly declined in distant areas at night, but unlike visitors, it was highest near major traffic routes along both main valleys during daytime. Comparison of weekdays displayed distinct patterns for passers-by, with elevated risk levels near major traffic routes in the Wipp Valley on the public holiday analyzed and significantly higher risk in remote areas during the weekend. In contrast, weekday patterns for visitors were less clear, apart from generally lower levels in remote areas on the public holiday and stronger variation during the weekend and the holiday.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that geolocalized mobile phone data can reveal spatiotemporal dynamics of natural hazards. Their ease of processing highlights the considerable potential for disaster risk research and management, where understanding spatiotemporal risk dynamics is essential.

Keywords: *Geolocalized Mobile Phone Data, Landslide Risk Analysis, Spatiotemporal Risk Dynamics, Exposure Assessment, Natural Hazards*

16 Positive Perspective on the Evolution of Socio-Ecosystem Resilience in the Anthropocene

Liang Emlyn Yang¹

¹Department of Geography, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich, Munich, Bavaria, Germany

Contact: emlyn.yang@lmu.de

The dominant discourse in global change science is currently defined by narratives of impacts and crisis, utilizing frameworks such as Planetary Boundaries and Tipping Points to diagnose biophysical risks. While essential for risk management, this focus often overshadows a parallel historical truth: the continuous and accelerating capacity of human societies to innovate and adapt. This study proposes a complementary, generative paradigm of positive resilience evolution. Defined as the emergent, co-evolutionary capacity of coupled socio-technological–ecological systems to sustain and enhance livability within a dynamic Earth, the positive perspective reframes humanity from a source of perturbation to a conscious agent of planetary stewardship.

The study articulates the theoretical foundations of this framework through five interactive pillars: Ecological Regeneration, Technological innovation, Social-culture Cohesion, Governance Intelligence, and Adaptive Actions. By integrating resilience theory with complex systems science, a capacity-oriented Resilience Index is established as a quantitative tool to track progress and identify high-leverage points for intervention. This perspective aims to move beyond descriptive vulnerability assessments toward prescriptive resilience engineering, emphasizing "bouncing forward" through intentional transformation. By highlighting documented resilience achievements and positive tipping points, this perspective provides a rigorous, evidence-based foundation for policy and practice.

Keywords: *Climate Resilience; Socio-ecosystem resilience; Sustainable transformation, Co-evolutionary capacity, Resilience metrics*

17 Application of Soil Erosion Modelling in Risk Management

Stefan Langel¹, Kerstin Hartsch¹, Michael von Werner¹

¹IPROconsult GmbH, Environmental consulting, Dresden, Germany

Contact: Stefan.Langel@iproconsult.com

Muddy floods caused by surface runoff and soil erosion during heavy rainfall events cause damage to buildings, infrastructure and surface waters. In particular, the deposition of sediment significantly increases the effort required for restoration and cleaning. In addition to this direct damage, indirect impacts due to the loss of system functionality may occur. Soil erosion itself represents a major form of soil degradation, threatening the finite resource of soil and reducing its fertility. Climate change intensifies these hazards through an increase in contrasting hydrological extremes, such as heavy rainfall and drought. These events have self-reinforcing effects; examples are the water repellency of dry soils and diminished vegetation cover caused by drought stress, which promote runoff and soil erosion. Erosion diminishes the water retention capacity of soil, thereby amplifying drought impacts and creating a self-reinforcing feedback loop.

17.1 Application of soil erosion modelling in risk management

The integration of muddy floods into established risk management concepts (for example for infrastructure) is recommended. A catchment-based approach following runoff and sediment transfer pathways and emphasizing prevention is essential. Given the limited availability of observational data and the high variability of influencing factors (precipitation, soil moisture, crop distribution, phenology and cultivation etc.), process-based simulation models, such as EROSION-3D, are used for scenario-based soil erosion hazard analysis. The integration of earth observation-based data products provides added value in accounting for temporal dynamics in land cover. EROSION-3D simulates runoff and sediment fluxes in the catchment area based on parameters of topography, rainfall intensity, soil characteristics (including soil texture, bulk density, soil moisture, resistance to erosion) and soil cover (vegetation/mulch cover, hydraulic roughness). Further use cases of soil erosion modelling in risk management include decision support for planning preventive soil and water retention measures (land-use changes or engineered measures) to build resilience, as well as the reconstruction of past events as part of post-event management. The use cases are illustrated by examples from Germany and Morocco.

17.2 Future perspectives towards multi-risk approaches

Approaches for the integration of soil erosion risks into multi-risk concepts can include the integration of soil erosion simulations into coupled modelling chains to analyse interactions between the different natural hazards (e.g. soil erosion and drought). For example, soil moisture and vegetation cover parameters could be used as interfaces between the coupled models. Further research into quantitative methods for assessing the vulnerability of infrastructure to damage from sediment deposition is also necessary.

Keywords: Muddy floods, Soil erosion, Heavy rainfall

18 Risk Modelling for Natural Hazard Related Threats to Railway Infrastructure with Reference to Tree Vitality

Elina Mevenkamp¹, Larissa Billig², Achim Bräuning³, Annett Frick¹, Kurtz, Wolfgang²; Sascha Gey¹, Nandini Hannak³, Martin Häusser³, Mathias Herbst², Randolph Klinke¹, Daniel Rutte, Daniel⁴, Benjamin Stöckigt¹; Sonja Szymczak⁴

¹LUP – Luftbild Umwelt Planung GmbH, Potsdam, Germany; ²German Meteorological Service, Agrometeorological Research Centre, Braunschweig/Oberschleißheim, Germany; ³Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nuremberg, Institute of Geography, Erlangen/Nuremberg, Germany; ⁴German Centre for Rail Traffic Research at the Federal Railway Authority, Bonn, Germany

Contact: elina.mevenkamp@lup-umwelt.de

Tree vitality is a key driver of natural hazard related risks for railway infrastructure, with forest stand edges being particularly susceptible to vitality loss. To ensure the long term resilience of rail transport through targeted vegetation management, regularly updated, spatially high resolution information on tree vitality is essential. This study develops a framework for dynamic and static risk modelling of natural hazard related railway risks, with a specific focus on tree vitality.

The drought driven risk to stand specific tree vitality and its influence on associated hazards, including windthrow, snow breakage, and slope fires, is analysed. Hydroclimatic conditions derived from historical data, together with synthetic scenarios, stress tests, and compound events, are used to capture the multiplicative effects of consecutive drought years. The resulting risk models are designed to support near real time risk assessment as well as short term forecasting of potential damage to railway infrastructure.

Keywords: *Risk modeling, railway infrastructure, natural hazard risks, tree vitality*

19 Windows That Open Narrow: How Extreme Events Narrow Adaptation Discourse

Sungju Han^{1,2*}, Jan Sodoge^{3,1*}, Maysaa Abdelmajid⁴, Larisa Tarasova⁴, Mairiana Madruga de Brito¹

¹Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department of Urban and Environmental Sociology, Leipzig, Germany; ²University of Potsdam, Institute of Environmental Science and Geography, Potsdam, Germany; ³Technopolis Group, Frankfurt, Germany; ⁴Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Department Catchment Hydrology, Leipzig, Germany

*Both authors contributed equally

Contact: sungju.han@ufz.de

Disasters are frequently described as "windows of opportunity" for climate adaptation, yet the conditions under which these windows open remain empirically underspecified. Using 265 million German newspaper articles (2000–2024) and automated text classification across 12 adaptation measure types, we link flood severity data from 1,582 gauging stations to adaptation discourse at the NUTS-3 district × week level (N = 281,160). Two-way fixed-effects models reveal that floods narrow rather than broaden adaptation discourse.

Methods

Floods were classified into five severity tiers using empirical return periods. Adaptation articles were identified via sentence-transformer classifiers (mean F1 = 0.77) and geolocated to NUTS-3 regions. Panel models include region and week fixed effects with NUTS-3 clustered standard errors.

Results

First, the media window opens only at severe and extreme floods: article volume increases 21-fold from minor to extreme severity, while moderate and major events produce statistically null effects. Chronic low-level exposure does not substitute for singular large shocks. Second, floods narrow discourse composition: structural measures (especially dikes) surge to 59% of coverage at extreme events, while financial coverage halves and nature-based solutions fall by two-thirds. An event-study across ~1,934 events reveals three post-flood phases — an immediate structural spike, a delayed financial peak around week 8, and a long-run governance collapse — with relocation and nature-based measures absent throughout. Third, cumulative flood experience gradually diversifies discourse, but exclusively through financial adaptation. Nature-based solutions and relocation remain unresponsive to both severity and experience at any temporal horizon.

Conclusions

Flood-triggered media discourse reinforces structural lock-in rather than enabling adaptive transitions. The measures most associated with transformative adaptation remain absent regardless of event severity or accumulated experience, suggesting that post-disaster windows may open narrow and close fast.

Keywords: *flood adaptation; media discourse; focusing events theory; text classification*

20 Innovative Geospatial Approaches to Multi-Risk Soil Erosion Assessment in Vulnerable Territories of Armenia: A Case Study of the Debed River Basin

Narek Harutyunyan¹

¹Yerevan State University, Department of General Geography, Yerevan, Armenia

Contact: n.harutyunyan@ysu.am

The article investigates soil erosion in mountainous environments, where complex geomorphological and hydrological conditions require integrated spatio-temporal analysis and advanced geospatial methods. The Debed River Basin in northern Armenia was selected as a representative case due to its pronounced topographic variability, diverse land-use patterns, and high erosion susceptibility. Findings provide a scientific basis for soil conservation, risk mitigation, and resilience-focused land-use planning, while demonstrating the applicability of advanced geospatial approaches to similar mountainous landscapes.

The study aims to assess and map soil erosion susceptibility in the Debed River Watershed using a GIS-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) framework with the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). It focuses on integrating topographic, hydrological, soil, vegetation, and land-use factors to identify erosion-prone areas and support sustainable land management and conservation planning.

Methods

The factors selected for erosion susceptibility assessment and mapping within the MCDA framework were weighted based on the study area's biophysical characteristics and information available in relevant literature. The relative importance of these erosion-related factors was systematically derived using the AHP. The procedure involved three key steps: construction of a pairwise comparison matrix, normalization of the matrix and computation of factor weights. This structured and reproducible approach ensured an objective determination of factor significance, providing a reliable basis for subsequent GIS-based susceptibility mapping and spatial analysis.

Findings

The Debed River Watershed is characterized by a highly dissected mountainous terrain with substantial elevation variability (up to 2818 m) and steep slopes, resulting in pronounced spatial heterogeneity of soil erosion susceptibility. Hydrology is primarily driven by snowmelt and precipitation (55 %) with notable groundwater contributions (45 %), and an average drainage density of 0.92 km/km² indicates moderate to high runoff connectivity. Using a GIS-based MCDA framework with AHP weighting, eleven erosion-related factors were integrated to produce an erosion susceptibility map, which classifies 65.9 % of the basin as very low risk, 33.9 % as low risk, and only 0.2 % as moderate risk. Higher susceptibility is concentrated on steep, sparsely vegetated, and erodible slopes, whereas gentle, vegetated, and cohesive soils exhibit minimal vulnerability, confirming the utility of integrated spatial and decision-analytic approaches for targeted watershed management and soil conservation.

Keywords: *streambank erosion, soil erosion, drainage density, land management*

21 Fragile Places: Rethinking Habitability in a Multi-Risk World

Christian Kuhlicke^{1,2}, Sungju Han^{1,2} and Samuel Rufat³

¹Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Leipzig, Germany; ²University of Potsdam, Germany; ³Ecole Polytechnique - CREST, France

Contact: Christian.Kuhlicke@ufz.de

Climate change is increasingly challenging the long-term viability of places across the globe. From flood-prone deltas and drought-affected rural regions to high mountain environments exposed to cascading hazards, many communities are confronted with interacting and accumulating risks. These developments point to the emergence of what we define as fragile places—territories where populations are repeatedly exposed to environmental hazards while lacking sufficient means to secure safe and sustainable living conditions over time (Rufat & Kuhlicke, 2025).

This contribution argues that focusing on habitability can advance geographical debates on risks and vulnerabilities (Sterly et al., 2025). Traditional risk frameworks often concentrate on hazards, exposure, vulnerabilities, probabilities and potential consequences of discrete events. While these perspectives are essential, they tend to overlook the lived realities of people in chronically exposed territories, where risks accumulate gradually rather than manifesting only through singular events.

A habitability perspective shifts attention toward long-term trajectories of risk accumulation and how they affect places and different groups of people, including repeated livelihood losses, gradual infrastructure degradation, mounting psycho-social stress, and the erosion of adaptive capacities. These cumulative processes can ultimately push places toward qualitative thresholds, where the conditions necessary for a viable and liveable environment become severely compromised. Such thresholds are rarely purely biophysical. They are socially contested, politically mediated and experienced differently. They are reshaped by patterns of inequality, governance capacities, and political decisions about whether—and for whom—habitability should be secured in exposed regions. Focusing on habitability therefore directs research beyond individual adaptation behaviour or household-level vulnerability toward the long-term viability of places, the structural processes that undermine them, and the political choices that shape risk management and territorial futures.

In the context of multi-risk environments, this perspective raises a new set of research questions. How do interacting hazards and chronic stressors gradually erode the habitability of places? When do cumulative pressures exceed the capacities of individuals, communities, and institutions to adapt, cope, and recover (and how to capture such processes)? And how can research better understand the qualitative and contested thresholds at which places transition from being risky to becoming effectively uninhabitable?

By foregrounding these questions, the presentation aims to stimulate discussion on how the concept of habitability can help reorient geographical risk and vulnerability research toward processes that shape the future of exposed places.

Discussion Points

- **From events to trajectories:** How can risk and sustainability research better capture long-term trajectories of risk accumulation—rather than focusing primarily on discrete hazard events and their probabilities?
- **Habitability thresholds:** How can researchers identify and analyse the qualitative and socially contested thresholds at which places shift from being risky to becoming effectively uninhabitable?
- **From vulnerable people to fragile places:** What does it mean for research to focus not only on vulnerable households or groups, but on the long-term viability of places and territories under multi-risk conditions?
- **The politics of habitability:** If the habitability of exposed regions is ultimately shaped by political decisions about investment, protection, and relocation, how should research better engage with these governance and justice dimensions?

References:

Rufat, S., & Kuhlicke, C. (2025). Climate Captivity: When in-situ Adaptation and Moving Out Are No Longer Options. *Progress in Environmental Geography*, 4(4), 393–411. <https://doi.org/10.1177/27539687251378494>

Sterly, H., Borderon, M., Sakdapolrak, P., Adger, N., Ayanlade, A., Bah, A., Blocher, J., Blondin, S., Boly, S., Brochier, T., Brüning, L., Bunchuay-Peth, S., O’Byrne, D., Safra De Campos, R., Nii Ardey Codjoe, S., Debève, F., Detges, A., Franco-Gavonell, M., Hathaway, C.,...Zickgraf, C. (2025). Habitability for a connected, unequal and changing world. *Global Environmental Change*, 90, 102953. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2024.102953>

Keywords: *qualitative thresholds, place-based research, inequality, risk accumulation, long-term trajectories*

22 Postgraduate Education for International Experts and Professionals in Disaster Risk Management and Civil Protection – Demands, Challenges and an Application

Annika Fröwis¹, Sophia Sternath¹, Philipp Marr¹, Thomas Glade¹

¹Institute for Geography and Regional Research, University of Vienna, Austria

Contact: annika.froewis@univie.ac.at

Natural hazards are increasing globally in frequency, intensity, and complexity due to global change. Climate change, urbanisation, and land-use changes are key drivers that intensify risks from events such as floods, wildfires, and landslides. This evolving risk landscape poses major challenges for society as well as for Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Civil Protection (CP) systems. Consequently, there is a growing demand for well-trained professionals capable of operating across sectors and national borders.

However, the current education and training landscape for DRM and CP experts shows significant gaps, particularly in postgraduate and international programmes. Existing programmes are often hazard-specific, thematically narrow, or nationally focused, limiting opportunities for cross-border and cross-sectoral collaboration. Addressing transboundary risks therefore requires an internationally oriented, interdisciplinary postgraduate education.

To meet this need, the EUMA project (Creating a European Higher Education Network for MAster's Programmes in Disaster Risk Management), developed within the Union Civil Protection Mechanism / Knowledge for Action in Prevention and Preparedness, established the Master's programme "International Disaster Management and Civil Protection". This programme provides a comprehensive foundation across prevention, preparedness, response, and recovery.

Building on this initiative, the follow-up project EUMApplus focuses on digitalisation and open-access provision of educational materials. It develops innovative digital formats, including Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) and podcasts, to advance accessibility to and long-term availability of high-quality training resources. This contribution demonstrates how the programme addresses existing gaps in international postgraduate DRM and CP education and presents digital education formats planned to be established within EUMApplus.

Keywords: *disaster risk management, civil protection, education, natural hazards*

23 Compound Climate Risks and the Prospects of Policy and Planning

Grard Hutter¹, Marco Neubert¹, Regine Ortlepp¹

¹Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER), Research Area Built Environment - Resources and Environmental Risk, Dresden, Germany

Contact: g.hutter@ioer.de

Looking at the one case of policy and planning for climate change adaptation in the city of Dresden, it is possible to see a complex and to some extent fragmented situation: In October 2025, city planners presented their new approach for considering climate change, blue-green infrastructures, and mobility issues more systematically in infill urban development ("Dreifache Innenentwicklung"). In December 2025, the new climate change adaptation concept of the city administration (with a lead by the environmental office) was rejected in the city council due to a new "rejection coalition" between conservative and far-right city councilors. At the moment, in an ongoing process, the Free State of Saxony, organized by the Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture, and Geology (LfULG), seeks to advance its climate change adaptation strategy with regard to the consideration of compound weather and climate events in the next strategy round (February 2027 onwards). Looking at these "real-world conditions", the presentation argues that adaptation research that takes compound events and risks into account needs also to address more systematically issues of policy and strategic planning. Therefore, the presentation gives some insights into ongoing work on strategic spatial planning for compound events and risks (including issues of adaptation pathways, urban resilience and scenario-planning) as well as research on climate policy in the face of populism (done mainly by others, e.g. political scientists).

References:

- Babalik, E., Frank, A. I., Sykes, O. (eds.) (2026). *The Routledge Companion to Comparative International Planning*. Milton Park/New York: Routledge.
- Boecher, M.; Jabra, D.; Zeigermann, U. (2022): Climate policy expertise in times of populism – knowledge strategies of the AfD regarding Germany's climate package. In: *Environmental Politics* 31(5), 820-840.
- Coaffee, J.; Lee, P. (2016). *Urban resilience. Planning for risk, crisis, and uncertainty*. Macmillan.
- Danke T., Hecht R., Hutter G. (2025): Reflecting on the Practice of Citizen Science Projects for Cities – the Case of "Colouring Dresden" in Germany. In: *Urban Research & Practice* 18(1), 142-150.
- Healey, P. (2009). In search of the "strategic" in spatial strategy making. In: *Planning Theory & Practice*, 10(4), 439–457.
- Rickards, L. et al. (2014). Opening and closing the future: Climate change, adaptation, and scenario planning. In: *Environment and Planning C: Government and Policy* 32, 587-602.
- Simpson, N. P. et al. (2023). Adaptation to compound climate risks: A systematic global stocktake. In: *iScience* 26, 105926.
- Zscheischler, J. et al. (2020). A typology of compound weather and climate events. In: *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment* 1(7), 333-347.

Keywords: *Enlarging intelligence, Framing selectively, Scenario planning, Urban resilience*